

Studies on Polybasic Acid Character of Some Hydrogen Vermiculites and Chlorites

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The nature and strength of acidity of colloidal acid clays isolated from some interstratified silicate minerals, vermiculites and chlorites, have been investigated electrometrically. The differences in the polybasic acid character on ageing are also reported. The chemical stability and multiple acid character depend on chemical composition, degree of lattice substitution and net negative charge in unit cell.

EXTENSIVE studies¹⁻⁸ have been made on the electrochemical character of colloidal acid clays belonging to layer lattice silicate minerals, kaolinites, illites, montmorillonites etc. Such studies are useful for (i) identification of clay minerals in soils, sedimentary rocks, etc., and (ii) control of soil acidity by necessary soil amendments (cf. lime treatment). Previous studies^{4,5,7} on acid clays have differentiated between two types of soil acidity, (a) active acidity (lower *pK* values) due to H_3O^+ , $Al(H_2O)_5^{3+}$ and (b) potential or latent acidity (higher *pK* values) due to monomeric and polymeric hydroxy Al, $Al(OH)^{2+}$, $Al(OH)_2^+$, $Al_6(OH)_{15}^{3+}$ and some other hydrolysis products of exchangeable Al with divergent *pK* values. On prolonged storage, acid character profoundly changes and becomes complicated due to the formation of multiple acid species of different acid strength⁵. Although much work has been done on this aspect, more data are desirable, specially, with respect to interstratified minerals, commonly found in soils and sedimentary rocks. With this objective, an investigation was undertaken for vermiculite and chlorite minerals to characterise (i) different types of acidity (cf. acid strengths and free energy changes of neutralisation of reacting acid species) in acid clays, (ii) changes in acidity on storage, and to correlate, (iii) acid characters with variations in chemical composition.

Experimental

Materials: The clay samples taken in this study were (i) vermiculites from Bagespura (Karnataka), Malavangatta (Karnataka) and Ranchi (Bihar), and (ii) chlorites from Kulu (Himachal Pradesh) and Nainital (Uttar Pradesh). These samples were collected from regions of different climatic zones as well as different geological setting and rock types of India.

Methods 1: Clay fractions ($< 2 \mu$) were isolated from powdered natural samples by the usual process of dispersion and sedimentation⁹, and were converted into homoionic H-form by passing through ion-exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120, H-form). The base exchange capacity (B.E.C.) values of these clays were determined by the standard procedures⁷. The structural formulae¹ for the clay minerals in the samples were determined from chemical analyses¹⁰ and are shown in Table 1.

The clay mineral components¹¹ of these samples were identified by X-ray data as Vermiculite with traces of interstratified vermiculite illite in Bagespura. Vermiculite with traces of illite vermiculite intergrades in Malavangatta, octahedral mica type biotite in Ranchi, and chloride with traces illite in Kulu.

TABLE 1 - STRUCTURAL FORMULAE OF H-CLAYS

Bagespura H-clay	$[(Si_{5.51} Al_{2.26} Fe_{.28}^{3+}) (Fe_{.96}^{2+} Fe_{1.58}^{3+} Ti_{.24} Mg_{2.42}) (Na_{.05}^{+} K_{.43}) O_{20} (OH)_4]^{-.72} H^{+.72}$
Malavangatta H-clay	$[(Si_{5.78} Al_{2.22}) (Al_{.25} Fe_{.36}^{3+} Fe_{1.67}^{3+} Ti_{.29} Mg_{2.80}) (Na_{.08}^{+} K_{.45}) O_{20} (OH)_4]^{-.45} H^{+.45}$
Ranchi H-clay	$[(Si_{6.67} Al_{1.33}) (Al_{1.27} Fe_{.34}^{3+} Fe_{.61}^{3+} Ti_{.15} Mg_{2.81}) (Na_{.05}^{+} K_{.87}) O_{20} (OH)_4]^{-.87} H^{+.87}$
Nainital H-clay	$[Si_{6.72} Al_{1.28}) (Al_{2.62} Fe_{1.1}^{3+} Fe_{1.47}^{3+} Ti_{.24} Mg_{4.92}) (Na_{.07}^{+} K_{.04}) O_{20} (OH)_{16}]^{-.15} H^{+.15}$
Kulu H-clay	$[Si_{7.04} Al_{.96}) (Al_{3.08} Fe_{1.1}^{2+} Fe_{.86}^{3+} Ti_{.95} Mg_{4.91}) (Na_{.20}^{+} K_{.2}) O_{20} (OH)_{16}]^{-.18} H^{+.18}$

Fig. 1. Alkali and pyridine titration curves of H-clay from Bagespura (○—○), Malavangatta (□—□), and Ranchi (△—△) samples.

Method 2: For alkali titrations, freshly prepared H-clay suspensions were equilibrated in a thermostatic bath at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ for 24 h in separate Jena flasks with increasing amount of 0.02 N NaOH (total volume 50 ml having 0.6% colloid (clay) content) and the pH and conductance values were measured by Elico glass electrode pH meter and Systronic conductivity bridge, respectively. For pyridine titration, freshly prepared H-clay suspensions were equilibrated similarly for 24 h with increasing amount of 0.1 N pyridine solution. The pH and conductance values were measured as before^{7,11}. The clay suspensions were allowed to age at room temperature for 75 days. Electrometric titrations of aged clays were performed with both alkali and pyridine. The free energy changes of neutralisation (ΔF_H) of clay acids at 30° were calculated from the equation⁷

$$\Delta F_H = 1395 (14.14 - pH).$$

The results of various electrometric titrations are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, and Tables 2 and 3.

Results and Discussion

The electrometric titrations of acid clays with strong and weak base are summarised in Tables 2 and 3 and illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2. The salient features of these findings are:

(i) Neutralisations of fresh acid clays (both vermiculites and chlorites) with strong base show two inflexion points in pH curves and two breaks in conductance curves, indicating dibasic acid character. The order of acid strength is of the sequence, Bagespura (pH 3.1, pK_1 4.0), Malavangatta (pH 3.37, pK_1 5.0), Ranchi (pH 4.27, pK_1 5.75), Nainital (pH 4.37, pK_1 6.15) and Kulu (pH 4.8, pK_1 6.55). Lattice substitution of Al for Si in tetrahedral silica sheet is 31.1 (Bagespura), 27.7 (Malavangatta), 16.6 (Ranchi), 16 (Nainital) and 12% (Kulu). Hydrogen clays are unstable and spontaneously change to H-Al system. The quantity of Al release and subsequent conversion to hydroxy-Al species in acid clays varies depending on the mineralogical make up and degree of interstratification (Table 1). First inflexion points (pH 6.5-8.65) are mostly due to

Fig. 2. Alkali and pyridine titration curves of H-clay from Kulu (O—O) and Nainital (⊙—⊙) samples.

neutralisation of active acid species, H_3O^+ , $[Al(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$, and the second inflexion points are observed at higher pH value (9.0-11.5) due to neutralisation of latent acid species of different hydroxy-Al. Free energy changes (ΔF_H) with neutralisation of active acid species is more than that of the corresponding neutralisation of potential acid species. On storage of acid clays, active acidity (exchangeable) decreases and potential (non-exchangeable) acidity increases. The pH of aged vermiculite clay sols change to 4.05-5.0, and that of aged chlorite clay sols increase to 5.15-6.1. The inflexion points in neutralisation of aged clay sols are observed at lower pH values in comparison to fresh clay sols. A composite mixture of hydroxy

Al, Fe and Mg cover non-exchangeable sites in planar and broken edge surfaces and the total titratable acidity decreases. Higher pK_a values of acid chlorite sols indicate that the amount of poly-aluminumhydronium cations formation is greater in chlorites than in vermiculites.

(ii) Electrometric titrations of acid clays with a weak base, pyridine (Table 3), show only one inflexion in pH curve and one break in conductance curve. Pyridine ($pK_b=8.8$) can neutralise active acidity (H_3O^+) but not the hydroxy Al species, monomeric and polymeric. From the inflexion points in pH curves and breaks in conductance curves, net Al release and chemical stability of acid

TABLE 2—ALKALI TITRATION DATA

Clay sample	B. E. C. meq/ 100 mg	Lattice substi- tution	Initial pH value (0.6% suspension)	At first inflexion point and break				At second inflexion point and break			
				pH	Meq. of NaOH/100 g H-clay	pK ₁	ΔF_H kcal mol ⁻¹	pH	Meq. of NaOH/100 g H-clay	pK ₂	ΔF_H kcal mol ⁻¹
Bagespura H-clay	78.0	31.1	3.10	6.5	61.0	4.0	10.66	9.0	84.0	4.3	1.17
Bagespura aged clay	—	—	4.05	5.3	43.0	4.25	—	.0	60.0	4.35	—
Malavangatta H-clay	49.92	27.7	3.37	7.6	46.0	5.0	9.13	9.4	66.0	5.8	6.61
Malavangatta aged clay	—	—	5.0	6.6	32.0	5.3	—	8.8	50.0	5.82	—
Ranchi H-clay	48.65	16.6	4.27	7.4	36.0	5.75	9.4	8.75	60.0	6.85	7.52
Ranchi aged clay	—	—	5.0	6.6	24.0	5.8	—	8.35	38.5	6.3	—
Nainital H-clay	13.93	16.0	4.37	8.65	11.0	6.15	7.66	11.5	20.0	7.6	3.68
Nainital aged clay	—	—	6.1	8.6	8.0	6.7	—	9.75	17.5	8.7	—
Kulu H-clay	15.28	12.0	3.8	8.45	13.5	6.55	7.94	9.6	23.0	7.5	6.34
Kulu aged clay	—	—	5.15	7.9	12.0	6.7	—	9.5	22.5	7.65	—

TABLE 3—PYRIDINE TITRATION DATA

Clay samples	B. E. C. meq/100 g	Initial pH value (0.6% suspension)	At inflexion point		pK value
			pH	meq pyri- dine/100 g H-clay	
Bagespura H-Clay	78.0	3.1	5.27	24.0	4.95
Bagespura aged clay	—	4.05	5.6	19.5	5.12
Malavangatta H-clay	49.92	3.37	4.9	25.0	4.35
Malavangatta aged clay	—	5.0	5.3	20.0	4.85
Ranchi H-clay	48.65	4.27	5.23	25.0	5.06
Ranchi aged clay	—	5.0	5.45	20.0	5.3
Nainital H-clay	13.93	4.37	6.0	20.0	5.7
Nainital aged clay	—	6.1	6.45	18.0	6.33
Kulu H-clay	15.28	3.8	6.15	24.0	5.9
Kulu aged clay	—	5.15	6.25	18.0	6.0

clays can be determined. pK_1 values from pyridine titrations are lower than that from alkali titrations. This shows that stronger alkali can neutralise some hydroxy Al species along with active acidity and shows higher inflexion points. On ageing, pyridine titrations show lower inflexion points due to loss of active acidity from the exchangeable sites similar to that of alkali titrations. An interesting feature is that the adsorption of pyridine on acid chlorites is higher than that of acid vermiculites, in spite of the fact that vermiculites are expanding lattice minerals and possess organophilic character. It is considered as due to part of pyridine adsorption on acid chlorites is made by Van der waal's forces.

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